

THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL ISSUES IN THE PHONETICS OF SOUND CHANGE

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Annotation: It has long been understood that speakers produce and listeners perceive non-random, systematic phonetic variants that serve as the raw material for sound change. This understanding underlies much of the current research on the phonetic underpinnings of change, which includes study of (i) general phonetic principles underlying variation, (ii) specific phonetic ‘preconditions’ and biases arguably linked to specific patterns of phonological instability and change, and (iii) the production and perception of variation by speaker-listeners in situations of actual ongoing change and by interacting agents in computational simulations of change. This paper shows how findings from these three broad areas of study have led to 21st century theoretical and empirical advancements in our understanding of phonetic change. Big-picture questions about the nature of change are approached through consideration of a series of smaller, more tractable questions (e.g., about the nature of, and relation between, innovative speaking and innovative listening for both stable patterns of variation and ongoing change). The paper’s goals are to show, for these questions, their theoretical grounding, empirical challenges, preliminary answers and, in turn, the new theoretical directions emerging from those answers.

Keywords: Sound change , phonetic variation , gestural overlap and reduction , perception-production relation , individual differences , origin and spread of change

INTRODUCTION

Study of the phonetic underpinnings of sound change has a long history in which early work identified some of the core principles that continue to guide phonetic investigations of sound change. As early as 1895, Baudouin de Courtenay (1895/1972), in delineating the stages of what is now referred to as phonologization (Hyman, 1976), determined that although the “conditioned

variants which depend on the phonetic environment ... may go unnoticed," their detection by listeners is "by no means excluded" (1972:174), in which case these variants may become regularized alternations that could lead to phonemic split in a given language. For example, according to Baudouin de Courtenay, context-dependent "embryonic" divergences in voicing might underlie now phonologized voicing assimilation in Polish and Russian (e.g., /d/ realized as [t] before /p/ but /t/ realized as [d] before /b/). Paul (1888) also identified small but systematic deviations in production, such as those that suit the "convenience of ... the organs of speech" (p. 50), as having the possibility of being perceived and becoming "a new creation from the old form" (p.54) within that speech community. These and other 19th century phoneticians recognized that speakers produce nonrandom, systematic phonetic variants that serve as the raw material for change. These scholars also recognized that listeners, who are variously attentive to these variants, might contribute to change by reproducing them in their own speech. The fundamental understanding that phonetic change is grounded in systematic phonetic variation has remained a cornerstone of 20th and 21st century approaches to change. Theories of the phonetics of sound change seek to explain phonetic variation and the forces that structure it in ways that capture how phonetic variation can contribute to, but need not result in, new articulatory and perceptual norms. Thus, theoretical approaches to change, like phonetic theories more broadly, study the articulatory and perceptual principles that give rise to variation. However, building on this shared theoretical foundation, phonetic theories of change especially address questions about how stable patterns of variation within a speech community become unstable patterns that lead to change; that is, they study how these basic principles apply to the initiation of change and, arguably, its spread through a community.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The modern school, foreign teachers - practical workers are working on the problem of developing students' cognitive activity by introducing new teaching methods, ideas and approaches to the learning process, influencing the formation of students' motivation, increasing it by strengthening the communicative orientation of the educational process. This contributes to the creation of a favorable atmosphere in the classroom for students, an increase in student interest in the subject and the development of a desire for practical use of a foreign language. Learning content consists of knowledge, skills, abilities, competencies, the mastery of which provides the ability to use language as a

means of communication, the formation and development of personality. In teaching a foreign language, expressive means play a huge role.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The nature of produced, perceived, and stored phonetic structures One influential development in phonetic theory is the increased emphasis on the dynamics of speech and especially the view that speech articulation can be represented in terms of vocal tract gestures. This perspective has been most explicitly developed in Articulatory Phonology (Browman & Goldstein, 1992; Pouplier & Goldstein, 2010), which holds that the gesture is the basic unit of speech. Gestures, which correspond to neither features nor segments, are dynamic actions of the vocal organs (e.g., lips, tongue tip, tongue dorsum, velum, glottis). As dynamic, physical events, gestures have extent in space and time; consequently, at any given moment in time, gestures overlap with each other. As one example, the tongue dorsum gesture for intervocalic [d] is largely determined by the flanking vowels, as can be seen for an American English speaker's productions of [idi], [ada], and [udu] in the ultrasound images in Fig. 1 (where the solid black contour in each set of images corresponds to maximum tongue tip raising for [d]). Such overlapping dynamic gestures give rise to timevarying, context-dependent acoustic variation. From a perceptual viewpoint, it is reasonable to assume that listeners attend to, and make use of, these regularities in the input signal. Theoretical approaches to perception that are especially compatible with the view that gestures are the basic unit of speech hold that listeners use the information in the input signal to perceive gestures (Liberman & Whalen, 2000; Goldstein & Fowler, 2003). For example, the Direct Realist theory of speech perception (Fowler 1986, 2018) postulates that listeners perceptually recover gestures by tracking the time-varying acoustic effects of coarticulated gestures. An important consequence of the gesturalist perspective is that it has broadly influenced the ways researchers think about, and study, the speech behaviors of speakers and listeners. Thus, regardless of whether the gesture is taken to be the basic unit of speech, there now appears to be general acceptance of the characterization of speech dynamics in terms of overlapping articulatory gestures (e.g., Ladefoged & Johnson, 2011: 69-72). There is, as well, increasing recognition, independent of assumptions about perceiving gestures, that the considerable but principled variation introduced by gestural overlap can facilitate perception. For example, results from eye-tracking studies, which monitor listeners' eye movements to visual displays in real time, indicate that, as the acoustic signal unfolds, listeners use anticipatory

information (e.g., information in vowels about upcoming consonants, as in neck vs net or bent vs bet) to disambiguate words more accurately (Dahan et al., 2001) and more quickly (Beddor et al., 2013) 2.1. What changes in sound change? ‘Sound change’ encompasses diverse phonological phenomena; these include assimilation and dissimilation, lenition and fortition, merger and split, addition and loss. Experimental approaches to the study of phonetic change need to offer an explanatory account for the full range. In doing so, these approaches especially focus on how general principles of human perception and production might contribute to phonological instability and change. One ‘general principles’ answer to ‘what changes in sound change?’ that has become increasingly influential in recent years is the proposal that all change, or nearly all change, can be linked to change in gestural overlap (coarticulation) or gestural reduction (undershoot). In an early proposal along this line, Browman & Goldstein (1991) not only linked casual speech processes to reduction in gestural magnitude and increase in overlap, but suggested that various types of sound change could be viewed as resulting from these two sources of variation. A yet stronger position has been taken in more recent work. For example, Bybee (2012) argued that the “phonetic path” to sound change (i.e., the path to sound change “proper”; 2012: 228) involves gestural retiming and reduction. Cronenberg et al. (2020) also situated change as nearly always arising out of the dynamic processes of gestural overlap and undershoot. Especially over roughly the past 10–15 years, this broad perspective has contributed to shaping the questions being asked, and the techniques being used, by studies of ongoing change and studies of synchronic variation that might give rise to instability. The answers that have emerged show how gestural dynamics underlie not only patterns of change that more obviously have their origins in overlap and reduction, such as assimilation and lenition/loss, but also some perhaps initially less obvious candidates, such as mergers (e.g., Lawson et al., 2013; Mielke et al., 2017) and splits (Harrington et al., 2018; Stevens et al., 2019). The answers also show the extent to which gestural reduction and overlap interact with each other and with aerodynamic and prosodic factors to give rise to change (e.g., Solé, 2010; Recasens, 2014: 3ff). As one illustration, consider nasal consonant (N) loss in the development

of distinctive vowel nasalization, where historical records from Romance and other languages show that N loss occurred first in voiceless (VNÇ) and only later in voiced (VNÇ) contexts (Hajek, 1997:141-143; Beddor, 2009) 2. Why do sounds change? I take as my starting point to addressing the general question

‘why do sounds change’ Ohala’s (1981, 1993, 2012) highly influential answer to a more specific question: what is the listener’s contribution to sound change, that is, why do sounds change in instances where change is arguably listenerbased? Ohala’s answer is shaped by the view that the speech signal is “inherently ambiguous” (1981: 178) with respect to its articulation. These ambiguities, which arise from vocal tract constraints that lead, for example, to gestural overlap, are understood as introducing noise into the signal–noise or distortions that listeners typically adjust for or factor out (see section 3.2). However, these perceptual adjustments may, on occasion, be imperfect and such imperfect accommodations have the potential to lead to change. For example, if, due to gestural overlap, a speaker produces a fronted [y]-like /u/ in the context of /t/ (e.g., English suit) or a nasalized vowel in the context of /n/ (e.g., bent) and a listener under- or hypo-corrects for that fronting or nasality—perhaps because the listener failed to detect the conditioning context—then that listener may interpret intended /ut/ input as /yt/ or /y/, or intended /en/ as /e ~n/ or /e ~/. As speaker, this ‘innocent misapprehender’ might, in turn, produce [y] or [e ~], as schematized in Fig. 2 for the latter outcome. As Ohala showed, the historical record of assimilatory changes is replete with instances of loss of the conditioning context but retention of the (originally) coarticulatory effect of that context. Thus, in Ohala’s approach, listeners contribute to sound change via misperception of speakers’ intended signals. However, the more recent perceptual evidence that listeners not only adjust for the acoustic consequences of gestural overlap, but also closely attend to those consequences (i.e., evidence emerging in part from gesturalist developments), raises the question of whether misperception indeed constitutes a consistent source of phonological change. That question leads, in turn, to a new one: if listeners are regarded as being generally accurate perceivers of coarticulated signals, how might they contribute to the (not uncommon) changes linked to gestural overlap that Ohala sought to explain? The approach to this question proposed by Beddor (2009, 2012; Beddor et al., 2018) rests on the understanding that the acoustic encoding of gestural dynamics provides listeners with useful information about what a speaker is saying. In addition, though, that approach crucially relies on findings that members of a speech community differ from each other: as speakers, individuals differ in patterns of produced coarticulatory overlap (section 3.1); as listeners, they differ in how useful that information is for perceptually differentiating speech contrasts (sections 3.2). By hypothesis, it is these non-errorful listener-specific differences in the relative perceptual weights of co-

occurring phonetic properties for a given contrast that have the potential to contribute to change. Revisiting the scenario for /en/ in Fig. 2, in Beddor's approach, members of an American English speech community produce gradient realizations ranging from [e~n] to [e ~] and have gradient perceptual weights, with some listeners requiring a nasal consonant but other listeners requiring only vowel nasality for a percept of, say, (b)en(t) (Beddor, 2012; Beddor et al., 2013). Change occurs gradually as community norms shift toward more innovative realizations and weights (in this case, more [e~]-like realizations and concomitant close attention to the vowel information). Recent apparent time studies of ongoing change provide supporting evidence of this type of gradual cue reweighting (e.g., Coetzee et al., 2018; Kuang & Cui, 2018; see section 4.2

CONCLUSION

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